

Source Water Assessment Plan

**Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Water Systems
Public Water System ID 084990003 and 084990002**

June 2016

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	5
Definitions.....	7
Introduction.....	8
Background.....	10
General Information.....	10
Description of Source Waters	12
Water System Information.....	15
Geologic Setting.....	19
Source of Water to Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs	26
Conceptual Model for Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs	27
Water Quality.....	31
Source Water Delineation.....	33
Zone A	33
Zone B.....	33
Zone C.....	34
Inventory.....	35
Methods.....	35
Inventory Results	36
Zone A Results.....	36
Zone B Results	41
Zone C Results	48
Inventory Update	55
Inventory Limitations.....	55
Susceptibility.....	56
Source Water Management.....	64
Citations	65
Appendix A.....	66

List of Figures

Figure 1. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Supply Systems with Source Water Delineation Zones A, B, and C.....	9
Figure 2. Uinta and Ouray Location Map.....	11
Figure 3. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Spring Collection Systems.....	13
Figure 4. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Supply Systems, Watershed Boundaries and Source-water Delineation Zones A, B and C.....	14
Figure 5. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Collection System (EPIC Engineering and Loughlin Water Associates LLC (2010).	16
Figure 6. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Water Systems and Consecutive Systems.	17
Figure 7. Uinta and Ouray Tribal Surface Ownership with Source-water Delineation Zones A and B	18
Figure 8. Geologic Structure - Uinta Mountains (Hansen, 1986).....	19
Figure 9. Uinta Mountain - Faults (Hansen, 1986).	20
Figure 10. Bedrock and Surficial Geology near Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs with Source-water Delineation Zones A, B, and C.	21
Figure 11. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs - Geology (Sprinkel, 2007, modified by EPIC Engineering and Loughlin Water Associates, LLC 2010).....	23
Figure 12. Geologic cross-section (Sprinkel, 2007), Uriah Heap Spring Location added by EPIC Engineering and Loughlin Water Associates, LLC (2010).	25
Figure 13. Whiterocks River, Canal and Whiterocks Spring Flows—1985 to 1995.....	26
Figure 14. Uinta River, Canal and Uriah Heap Spring Flows—1985 to 1995.	27
Figure 15. Block Diagram of Conceptual Model for Springs (Lambert and Others, 2011).	28
Figure 16. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs - Capture Zones	30
Figure 17. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Supply Systems - 100-Year Flood Plain near Source-water Delineation Zones A and B.....	37
Figure 18. Roads and Canals near Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Spring (EPIC Engineering and Loughlin Water Associated (2010).	38
Figure 19. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Supply Systems - Specific Land Use near Source-Water Delineation Zone A within Zone B.	39
Figure 20. Big Spring with Source-water Delineation Zones A and B.	40
Figure 21. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Supply Systems - Potential Contaminant Sources in Source-water Delineation Zone B.....	42
Figure 22. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Supply Systems - Land Use within Source-water Delineation Zone B.	47
Figure 23. Sub-type of Land Use within Source-water Delineation Zone B.....	48
Figure 24. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Supply Systems - Potential Contaminant Source in Source-water Delineation Zone C.	50
Figure 25. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Supply Systems - Specific Land Use within Source-water Delineation Zone C.....	52
Figure 26. Sub-type of Land Use within Source-water Delineation Zone C.....	53

List of Tables

Table 1 - Zone A: Potential Contaminant Sources	36
Table 2 - Zone B: Potential Contaminant Sources.....	45
Table 3 - Zone C: Potential Contaminant Sources.....	53
Table 4 - Zone A: Susceptibility Ratings.....	57
Table 5 - Zone B: Susceptibility Ratings.....	59
Table 6 - Zone C: Susceptibility Ratings.....	62

Source Water Assessment Plan

Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Water Systems Public Water System ID 084990003 and 084990002

Executive Summary

This report assesses the sources of water that are used for the Whiterocks and Uriah Heap drinking water systems, and an evaluation of Big Spring. Potential contaminant sources that could be a threat to the drinking water system are inventoried and given susceptibility ratings that indicate the level of potential threat to the drinking water system. This report is based on the U.S. EPA (2014) initial assessment and represents inventoried contaminant threats and the plan for protecting the drinking water systems.

The Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Systems are comprised of two spring collection systems and a make-up well that serves as a backup water supply. Big Spring, a ceremonial source of water was included in this assessment at the request of the Ute Tribe. The water is treated with chlorination at a new treatment plant (2014) before storage (7 tanks) and distribution to the communities of Whiterocks, Fort Duchesne, Gusher, Randlett, Ballard, Roosevelt City, Independence, and Ouray. The source waters are located in a relatively remote area to the north and south of the community of Whiterocks.

The source water delineation areas for the Whiterocks and Uriah Heap systems utilize a hybrid approach of the groundwater and surface water methods based on the State of Utah guidelines for ground water, R309-600 (2012) and for surface water, R309-605 (2001). Delineation areas are comprised of 3 main zones. Zone A is based on the groundwater method and it extends from the source waters outward a distance of 100 feet. Zone B is based on the surface water method and it extends 15 miles upstream of the source waters with a ½ mile buffer on each side of the surface water. Zone C includes upper Whiterocks River and Uinta River, and the tributaries that have the potential to contribute contamination. Zone C extends up to 65 miles upstream, but limited to watershed boundaries, with a buffer of 1000 feet on both sides of the streams. A special delineation zone was created to protect Big Spring using the groundwater and surface water methods. The Whiterocks and Uriah Heap source waters were determined to be moderately to highly vulnerable to contamination. This is mainly a result of the influence of surface water on the springs and the potential contaminants in the surface water. The new water treatment plant which replaced the two older treatment plants receives water from the Whiterocks Spring and Uriah Heap Spring and treats the water to meet U.S. EPA drinking water standards. The most notable potential sources of contamination include overhead and adjacent unlined canals, a nearby oil well, a gas station, runoff from irrigated land, and other natural and anthropogenic sources.

After the assessment of potential sources of contamination in the source water protection zones, management of the potential contaminants would be the next step. A source water protection plan would describe ways the community intends to protect the source water. This plan could include ideas for public education, best management practices for environmentally friendly land use, identifying setback distances from the river for agricultural and industrial use, and a contingency plan that addresses potential emergency situations that might be affecting the supply of water. The ultimate goal of source water protection is to incorporate the entire watershed in the protection plan, in addition to the delineation area. Protecting the entire watershed is the most comprehensive way to maintain high quality source water for all systems utilizing Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs as a water source.

Note on ArcGIS generated map figures: All map figures, generated from ArcGis (those with the BING maps background), are printed in this document at 75% of their original size (8.5 in x 11.0 in). Please see the associated .pdf file, U&O_SWP_ArcGis_Figures_Binder1_62116 to see the full sized figures and for more detail.

Definitions

Best Management Practice - Methods that have been determined to be the most effective, practical means of preventing or reducing pollution from non-point sources.

Delineation – Method of mapping a source-water protection area. For surface water systems delineation is established by the distance in miles from the intake. For groundwater systems, delineation is based on the distance from the well a contaminant will travel in a certain amount of time.

Maximum Contaminant Level (MCL) - The maximum permissible level of a contaminant in water which is delivered to any user of a public water system.

Non-point Source Pollution - Pollution sources that are diffuse, without a single identifiable point of origin, including runoff from agriculture, forestry, and construction sites.

Point-source Pollution – Point-source pollution refers to the pollution that comes from a specific, identifiable source, such as a pipe, gas line, channel or leaking storage tank.

Potential Contaminant Source – A location where there is an activity having the potential to release contaminants into the environment at a level of concern. The activity may be associated with a business, industry, or operation involving the use, transport, storage, or manufacture of the potential contaminants. Identification of a business, industry or operation as a **potential contaminant source** does not mean that the business, industry or operation is out of compliance with any local, state, or federal regulation, and it does not necessarily mean that the business, industry or operation has or will cause contamination. What it does mean is that the potential for contamination (or pollution as it is sometimes called) exists due to the nature of the business, industry, or operation. An inventory of potential contaminant sources can:

- Provide an effective means of educating the public about potential contaminants;
- Provide information on the locations of potential sources, especially those that present the greatest risks to the water supply; and
- Provide a reliable basis for developing a local management plan to reduce the risks of contamination to the water supply.

Susceptibility – Potential for a public water system to draw water contaminated by a potential source of contamination at concentrations that may pose a concern.

Synthetic Organic Compounds - Chemicals commonly used in pesticides, herbicides, plastics, and fuels.

Ultrafiltration - A process for removing particulate matter from water using a pressure induced separation of solutes from a solvent through a semi permeable membrane.

Volatile Organic Compounds - Any organic compound which evaporates readily to the atmosphere and commonly found in gasoline, paint, solvents, plastics, and adhesives.

All definitions, unless otherwise noted, were taken from EPA's Term References System at:
http://iaspub.epa.gov/sor_internet/registry/termreg/searchandretrieve/termsandacronyms/search.do

Introduction

Contaminated water is not only a health concern but is also expensive to remediate or replace. The assessment is a proactive approach that identifies potential contaminants and details the susceptibility of the source water to contamination. Springs, which may be recharged by surface water, may be additionally susceptible to contamination because of the way in which spring systems operate hydrologically. This assessment, further, may be used by officials to develop a source water protection plan that details a management plan for protecting the source water.

By keeping contaminants from reaching the drinking water source, the cost savings may not only be from treatment costs or costs developing an alternative source of water but could also come from reduced sampling and monitoring requirements of the source water. There are four steps of a source water assessment: 1) Delineating the source-water areas contributing to the public-water supply source; 2) Making an inventory of possible contaminant sources within the source-water delineation areas; 3) Outlining the susceptibility of water system to contaminants through the source-water delineation zones; and 4) Informing the public of the findings.

This report discusses the Whiterocks and Uriah Heap water system characteristics, shows the delineation zones for the water sources, discusses potential contaminants, and discusses the vulnerability of the water system. Delineation is defined as the mapping of the area that influences the source water. For this report, the delineation zones will include Zone A, the sensitive/critical area, within 100 feet of the make-up well, source springs, and Big Spring, the Zone B sensitive/critical area which extends 15 miles upstream from the sources and ½ mile on both sides of the streams, and Zone C, which includes upper Whiterocks and Uinta Rivers and tributaries, and extends up to the watershed boundaries and 1000 feet on both sides of the streams. These delineation zones encompass areas that have been determined to be susceptible to potential contamination (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Supply Systems with Source Water Delineation Zones A, B, and C.

Background

General Information

The community of Whiterocks is located in Uintah County within the jurisdictional boundary of the Uintah and Ouray Indian Reservation, located in the northeast portion of Utah (Figure 2). The Uintah and Ouray Reservation encompasses roughly 4.5 million acres in five counties: Carbon, Duchesne, Grand, Uintah, and Wasatch. The Whiterocks River flows southward past the community of Whiterocks where it joins the Uinta River. The area around the intakes consists of gently sloped flood plains of the Whiterocks River and the Uinta River; the Whiterocks and Uriah Heap springs occur along the boundary where the flood plains meet.

The community of Whiterocks has a permanent population of 289 people according to the 2010 U.S. Census, a decrease compared to the 2000 population of 341. The total number of connections to the system as of 2013 was about 1400; the service area includes the communities of Whiterocks, Fort Duchesne, Gusher, Randlett, Ballard, Roosevelt City, Independence, and Ouray.

The weather in this region is classified as semi-arid with low precipitation and high evaporation rates. The immediate area receives an average of less than nine inches of precipitation annually, but the Uinta Mountains to the north receive significant amounts of snow. The spring snow melt provides plenty of water for the rivers and the extensive canal distribution system.

Figure 2. Uinta and Ouray Location Map

Description of Source Waters

The sources of water for the system are the Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs. The springs are located to the east and southeast of the community of Whiterocks. These springs occur along the boundary between the Whiterocks River flood plain and the Uinta River flood plain. The springs are supplied from shallow groundwater that is thought to be recharged by the Whiterocks River and the network of unlined canals fed by the Whiterocks and Uinta Rivers. The spring water is collected through a network of about 6800 feet of perforated pipes at a depth of 9 to 20 feet at two locations, Whiterocks Springs and Uriah Heap Springs (Figure 3).

The Whiterocks River and Uinta River watershed boundaries are shown in Figure 4. Whiterocks River consists of 5 smaller watersheds, West Fork Whiterocks River, East Fork Whiterocks River, Paradise Creek-Whiterocks River, Lower Whiterocks River, and part of Uriah Heap Springs. Uinta River consists of 7 smaller watersheds, Shale Creek – North Fork Uinta River, Atwood Creek – Uinta River, Clover Creek – Uinta River, Pole Creek, Hominy Creek – Farm Creek, Cart Hollow – Uinta River, and part of East Channel Uinta River. A Total Maximum Daily Load (TMDL) report for the Uinta River watershed includes Whiterocks River watershed as a tributary to the Uinta River.

Figure 3. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Spring Collection Systems

Figure 4. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Supply Systems, Watershed Boundaries and Source-water Delineation Zones A, B and C.

Water System Information

The Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Systems serve approximately 1400 connections in the service area, as of 2013. The water systems sources consist of two spring collection galleries and a make-up well. The water from these sources is fed into the new treatment plant, Figure 5, and then stored in 7 storage tanks before distribution. Storage tanks consist of the Whiterocks Tank, the Ouray Tank, a Gusher Tank, the Bottle Hollow #1 Tank, the Bottle Hollow #2 Tank, a new 300,000 gallon tank, and a new 1,000,000 gallon tank. The finished water is then distributed to the residents in the community of Whiterocks, and to downstream communities in Fort Duchesne, Gusher, Randlett, Ballard, Roosevelt City, Independence, and Ouray. As of 2013, Figure 6, there were 500 full-time residents connected to the Whiterocks Water System (R = 500) and 1,400 full-time residents (R = 1,400) connected to both Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Systems. Whiterocks Water System flows into Uriah Heap Water System. The Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Systems supply the Ballard Water Improvement Water District (UT-240010), South Ballard, Utah, Ouray Park Water Improvement District (UT-2401400), Randlett, Utah, and Johnson Water Independent Water Supply (UT-2404200), Roosevelt, Utah. As of 2013 there were approximately 950 full-time residents connected to the Ballard Water Improvement Water District system, 250 full-time residents connected to the Ouray Park Water Improvement District system, and 100 full-time residents connected to the Johnson Water Independent Water Supply system.

Uriah Heap and Whiterocks Distribution System

Figure 5. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Collection System (EPIC Engineering and Loughlin Water Associates LLC (2010).

Figure 6. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Water Systems and Consecutive Systems.

Another spring known as “Big Spring” is located in the adjacent Uinta River valley. This spring is not connected to any treatment or distribution systems. It is used primarily as a historically and culturally significant source of water for ceremonial purposes among all Ute tribal members from all reservations. Discussion with Tribal representatives revealed that the spring water is considered to be pristine and beneficial to tribal health, and has been confirmed in water samples described in the previous section.

Outlying residents depend on water from wells and water delivery services. Well water in the area has been reported by some residents to taste and/or smell strange. Well water in the area should be sampled and tested to determine if any potentially unhealthy conditions exist.

Surface ownership of tribal and non-tribal lands related to Zones A and B is shown in Figure 7. Many types of ownership exist in the source-water protection areas, and this fact highlights the complexity of the Whiterocks and Uriah Heap systems, their related public water supply, and distribution.

Figure 7. Uinta and Ouray Tribal Surface Ownership with Source-water Delineation Zones A and B

Geologic Setting

The area discussed in this report is located in the northern area of the Uinta Basin, south of the Uinta Mountains. The Uinta Mountains are an east – west trending mountain range in the northeastern part of Utah bordering Wyoming and continuing into western Colorado formed during the Laramide Orogeny 70 – 34 million years ago (Sprinkel, 2014). Stratigraphy of the Uinta Mountains is made up of the Neoproterozoic rocks of the Uinta Mountain Group overlain by a thick sequence of sedimentary Paleozoic through Mesozoic formations and finally Tertiary and Quaternary deposits (Appendix A, Sprinkel (2007)).

The Uinta Mountains have more peaks above 11,000 feet in elevation than any other range in Utah. Many authors have reported on the geology of the Uinta Mountains, including Hansen (1986), Figure 8, who describes the Uinta Mountains underlain by a large anticlinal structure and bordered by faults on the north and south, Figure 9 (Hansen, 1986). The northern fault is related and correlative to the Cheyenne Belt suture zone, a weak zone formed in the crust from plate tectonic movements roughly 1.7 billion years ago when the Wyoming Province converged with the younger Yavapai-Mazatzal province (Sprinkel, 2014). This east – west suture zone and related faulting controlled the east – west trend of the Uinta Mountains. On the south side of the range is a smaller, but still significant fault, called the basin bounding fault. More recent geologic mapping by Sprinkel (2014) has revealed two anticlinal structures, one underlying the western Uinta Mountains and another underlying the eastern Uinta Mountains, and evidence of a fault zone separating them. The two anticlinal structures are responsible for the difference in characteristics across the overall range. The western Uinta Mountains are higher in elevation and have undergone more glaciation than the eastern portion of the Uinta Mountain range which is lower in elevation and trends slightly to the southeast. Sprinkel (2014) discusses evidence for a newly inferred northwest trending fault zone the range separating the two anticlinal structures and may have been active through the late Tertiary and Quaternary because of fault scarps in Pleistocene gravel deposits and earthquake data. Concurrent with the Laramide orogeny, the Sevier orogeny (130 – 40 million years ago) impacted the structure of the western Uinta Mountains through thrust faulting forces.

Figure 8. Geologic Structure - Uinta Mountains (Hansen, 1986).

Figure 9. Uinta Mountain - Faults (Hansen, 1986).

The Uinta Mountains consist of the Precambrian rocks of the Uinta Mountain Group and the Red Pine Shale, the Cambrian rocks of the Lodore Formation, the Mississippian rocks of the Madison Limestone, Humbug Formation, and Doughnut Shale, the Pennsylvanian rocks of the Round Valley Limestone, the Permian rocks of the Weber Sandstone, the Triassic rocks of the Moenkopi Formation and Chinle Formation, the Jurassic rocks of the Nugget Sandstone, Entrada Sandstone, and the Morrison Formation, the Cretaceous rocks of the Dakota Sandstone, Mancos Shale, and Mesa Verde Group, the Eocene rocks of the Wasatch Formation, Green River formation, Uinta Formation, and Duchesne River Formation, the Oligocene rocks of the Duchesne River Formation and Bishop Conglomerate, the Quaternary sediments of the Glacial Alluvial Outwash, Piedmont and Basin Alluvium, and Flood Plain and Channel Alluvium. The surface deposits are mostly glacial drift and alluvial fill. The stratigraphic column, Appendix A (Sprinkel, 2007) describes the formations and lithology in more detail. A generalized geologic map of the Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs area is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Bedrock and Surficial Geology near Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs with Source-water Delineation Zones A, B, and C.

Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs are located in the northern part of the Uinta Basin in the Quaternary glacial alluvial outwash deposits (Qga), close to the contact with Quaternary piedmont and basin alluvium deposits (Qa), shown in Figure 11 (Sprinkel, 2007). The geography of the area is dominated by pediments along the base of the mountains, flood plains along the rivers, local plateaus, benches, and badlands. The flood plains of the Whiterocks River and the Uinta River meet east of the community of Whiterocks and form a northwesterly trending boundary between the two flood plains. It is along this boundary that the Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs occur. The glacial alluvial outwash overlies the Brennan Basin Member of the Duchesne River Formation in the northern area or the Lapoint Member of the Duchesne River Formation in the southern area, shown in the geologic cross-section (Figure 12). The outwash deposits are mainly boulders to pebbles and sand deposits derived from the high-energy meltwater of ancient glaciers. Outwash deposits create a prolific aquifer where sufficiently thick and saturated. Pediment alluvium and stream-deposited alluvium also occur in the area but these deposits are too thin to be important aquifers. Groundwater levels are generally at the elevation of the rivers and streams and within 5 to 15 feet of the surface in all other areas.

Geologic Map: Sprinkel (2007), Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs locations added by EPIC Engineering and Loughlin Water Associates, LLC (2010).

Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs - Geology

Figure 11. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs - Geology (Sprinkel, 2007, modified by EPIC Engineering and Loughlin Water Associates, LLC 2010).

- Qga** GLACIAL ALLUVIAL OUTWASH, UNDIVIDED (PLEISTOCENE) - Unconsolidated, well-rounded, mostly red quartzose sandstone and quartzite (Uinta Mountain Group) boulders to pebbles and sand deposits in the Whiterocks Canyon drainage in the northwest part of the quadrangle (see Sprinkel, 2006) derived from the high-energy meltwaters of glaciers of undetermined age; thickness not determined but probably less than 10 m.
- Qa** PIEDMONT AND BASIN ALLUVIUM, UNDIVIDED (HOLOCENE AND PLEISTOCENE[?]) - Variably consolidated, poorly to moderately sorted sand, gravel, cobbles, and boulders deposited on near-planar bedrock surfaces; more than one level recognized but not subdivided so deposits of different ages can share a common boundary; poorly to well-developed soil profile developed in all levels with the best-developed profile in the topographically highest deposit; less than 2 m thick.
- Tdl** LAPOINT MEMBER OF DUCHESNE RIVER FORMATION (OLIGOCENE AND EOCENE) - Light-reddish-brown and yellowish-gray, fine-grained sandstone, siltstone, and mudstone; contains abundant light-greenish-gray bentonite beds; mostly nonresistant and thin- to very thin bedded; late Eocene (Duchesnean) in age based on vertebrate fossil assemblage and K-Ar age (mineral not reported) of 39.3 Ma from an ashy siltstone bed at the Lapoint-Dry Gulch Creek contact (Anderson and Picard, 1972); three K-Ar ages on biotite of 35.7 to 40.3 were obtained from near the base of the Lapoint Member (McDowell and others, 1973; Mauger, 1977); exposed thickness 120 m, but as much as 300 m thick in subsurface of Uinta Basin.
- Tdd** DRY GULCH CREEK MEMBER OF DUCHESNE RIVER FORMATION (EOCENE) - Medium-reddish-brown and purplish-gray, fine-grained sandstone, siltstone, mudstone, and conglomerate; dominated by slope-forming siltstone and mudstone with ledge-forming thin-bedded sandstone; contains some vertebrate fossils (Anderson and Picard, 1972); less than 150 m thick.

FAULTS

Steeply dipping - Dashed where approximately located; dotted where concealed; bar and ball on downthrown side where offset is known

Reverse - dotted where concealed; teeth are on upthrown side

Thrust - concealed, teeth are on upthrown side

FOLD AXIS

Anticline - Dashed where approximately located; dotted where concealed

Syncline - Dashed where approximately located; dotted where concealed

Overtaken syncline - Dotted where concealed

Monocline - Dotted where concealed

Figure 12. Geologic cross-section (Sprinkel, 2007), Uriah Heap Spring Location added by EPIC Engineering and Loughlin Water Associates, LLC (2010).

The thickness of the glacial alluvial outwash deposits has not been directly measured, as noted by Sprinkel (2007), but probably is no thicker than 32 feet and the thickness of the piedmont and basin alluvium deposits is estimated to be approximately 6.5 feet. The axes of two synclines trend northwest between the two springs interposed between corresponding northwest trending thrust faults.

Big Spring is fed by groundwater at the contact of the Madison Limestone with the Duchesne River Formation. The recharge area for the limestone aquifer that feeds Big Spring could be extensive and extend further than the source water delineation zone shown later. Travel times in limestone and karst terrains can be relatively quick compared to other systems because of the nature of karst systems and dissolution in the limestone. Dissolved calcium from the limestone influences the color and turbidity of the water in the spring.

Source of Water to Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs

According to the results of a previous study by EPIC Engineering and Loughlin Water Associates, LLC (2010), the peak flows of surface water (Whiterocks River, Uinta River, and associated canals) in the spring of the year correspond to increased spring flows after 1 to 2 months. There is a lag associated with the time of travel for the surface water to impact the water at the depth of the collection pipes. This correlation is shown in Figures 13 and 14, and demonstrates most likely surface water impacts groundwater that feeds the springs. This possible interconnection would make the springs highly vulnerable to contamination at the surface.

Figure 13. Whiterocks River, Canal and Whiterocks Spring Flows—1985 to 1995.

Figure 14. Uinta River, Canal and Uria Heap Spring Flows—1985 to 1995.

An inspection of the collection pipes in both spring collection systems in 2010 by EPIC Engineering revealed that there were problems with roots and sedimentation in the collection pipes. Some sections of the pipes are cracked and in need of replacement. They recommend that the whole system needs to be cleaned and flushed out. Additionally, rodent droppings were found in a previous sanitary survey inspection of the treatment plant in 2008 by Mr. Bud Spillman. During a field visit by EPA staff in the spring of 2014 a newly constructed treatment plant that processes the combined water from both springs was observed and is operational as of spring 2014. The previous treatment plants have been taken off line and disconnected as they are being decommissioned.

Conceptual Model for Whiterocks and Uria Heap Springs

A conceptual site model (CSM) represents the current understanding of a site including boundaries, natural setting, physical characteristics, land activities and infrastructure per ASTM (2008). In the case of Whiterocks and Uria Heap Springs, the CSM is more accurately termed a conceptual model (U.S. EPA, 2016) which will focus on the geology and hydrology of the springs to describe the way in which the system works including prior ideas, inputs to the system comprised of recharge and capture zones, outputs, boundaries, and other information. A further use of the conceptual spring model is to assist in protecting the quality of the spring water, and also to provide general, qualitative information on quantity and supply of water to the springs over time. As more data are gathered, the conceptual model will change over time.

Prior ideas regarding Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs, in specific, the hydrology in the area, are discussed in the EPIC Engineering and Loughlin Water Associates (2010) and Lambert and Others (2011) reports. EPIC Engineering and Loughlin Water Associates (2010) state “Spring flow from Whiterocks Spring and Uriah Heap Spring generally peaks several months after peak flow in Whiterocks River... The ultimate source of water discharged by these springs is primarily infiltration from the Whiterocks River, irrigation canals and irrigated land”.

Lambert and others (2011) studied ground-water and surface-water interactions approximately 2 miles south of Whiterocks encompassing the Sprouse Well Field and the Uinta River, a mile and a half west of the Uriah Heap Springs. The authors illustrate a general conceptualization of the ground water and surface water systems in the Roosevelt Valley, Figure 15. The main aquifer in the area is in the alluvial glacial outwash which is recharged from underflow from higher elevations toward the mountains in addition to percolation from nearby streams and river, irrigation water and precipitation. Ground water flow in the unconfined aquifer is to the southeast and Lambert and others (2011) noted there were seasonal water level variations in wells completed in the alluvial glacial outwash aquifer, with higher water levels in late spring to early summer and lower water levels mid-winter. Discharge of the shallow, unconfined ground water is by evapotranspiration at the water table, discharge to springs, canals and rivers, and artificial withdrawal of ground water from wells. Underlying the alluvial glacial outwash aquifer is the confined Duchesne aquifer.

Figure 15. Block Diagram of Conceptual Model for Springs (Lambert and Others, 2011).

Information from Lambert and others (2011), along with Figure 15, provide the foundation for the current conceptual model. Recharge to the Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs appears to be a result of infiltration from precipitation, recharge from local rivers, streams, and canals, and lateral inflow from higher elevations in the same drainage basin, Figure 7. Evidence for the source of water to the springs are: 1) Spring flows vary with flows in the Whiterocks and Uinta Rivers (Figures 13 and 14), though a lag of approximately two months between high flow in the rivers corresponds to higher spring flow; 2) Roots were found upon inspection of the spring systems indicating inflow from the surface (EPIC Engineering, 2010, p. 1); and 3) Chemistry of the spring waters compared to river and canal water (to be completed) could provide more information on the source of water to the springs.

Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Spring boundaries can be summarized as follows: The springs are located in glacial alluvial outwash deposit, close to the contact with Quaternary piedmont and basin alluvium deposits, in the glacial outwash aquifer near the confluence of the rivers. The glacial alluvial outwash deposit is relatively thin, around 30 m (98 ft) (Sprinkel, 2007). Local drainage divides, and river boundaries are the most likely provide the lateral boundaries (in map view) of recharge to the springs. In addition, the springs themselves may be the southern boundary because of their discharge. Flow in water-table and river is to the south-southeast. Boundaries for the two systems are slightly different. Whiterocks Springs most likely are bounded, hydrologically on the west by the Whiterocks River and to the north, and east by the watershed (topographic drainage) divide. Uriah Heap Springs are most likely bounded hydrologically on the west by the east channel of the Uinta River and to the north and east by the watershed (topographic drainage) divide, Figure 16, showing local watersheds/drainage divides; Proposed capture zone for the Whiterocks and Uriah Heap springs; and Source-water Protection Zones A – C.

Figure 16. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs - Capture Zones

Water Quality

The water supply has been sampled on a monthly basis for over 20 years as required of public water supplies. These results were reviewed and it was found that coliform was detected in the water samples taken on Feb. 20, 2013, and again on Apr. 30, 2013. Subsequent sampling has not detected any problems with contamination.

Streams, canals, springs, and wells have been sampled periodically and recorded since 1941. These data contain water quality information based on inorganic compounds, organic compounds, metals and metalloid positive ions, negative ions, synthetic compounds, dissolved gasses, and radon. These data were located in, and downloaded from the NWIS (National Water Information System) database that is maintained by the U. S. Geological Survey. There were 10 well records, 16 spring records, and 10 stream records found for the area within all delineation zones.

Of the 10 well records, 4 were for oil and gas wells and the other 6 were for water wells. Water was sampled in all of these wells by either the USGS WRD or an unspecified source. The 6 water wells represent conditions within 200 feet of the surface, or the water table aquifer. The oil and gas wells represent conditions at depths between 5000 feet and 8000 feet below the surface. Secondary Standard (SCL) is a non-enforceable level specified by the EPA for contaminants that may cause cosmetic or aesthetic effects and should not be confused with Maximum Contaminant Level (MCL). The 6 water wells have elevated levels of calcium, magnesium, sodium, potassium, chloride, and sulfate. Of these levels, the calcium levels are 20 to 50 times the SCL of 1.3 mg/l, and the sulfate levels are 7 to 45 times the SCL of 1.3 mg/l. Neither of these pose a threat to human health, but the water may have a slightly 'salty' taste. The 4 oil and gas wells which were sampled at much deeper depths have higher levels of all constituents. Since the southern area of delineation zone 2 is at the margin of the Uinta Basin, the location of these wells reflects this in the samples. Two of the four wells have normal levels except for sulfate, while the other two have extremely high values of these constituents. The Total Dissolved Solids for these two wells are 17,000 and 4400 mg/l, well above the generally accepted SCL of 500 mg/l. Based on the lack of additional data it is unclear why there is so much variability in the samples. Additionally, sodium and chloride are exceptionally high. The sample depths of these two wells are within a saline aquifer, and the sample intervals of the other two wells don't correspond to this saline aquifer. The screened depths of the samples are not identified, so the variation of salinity could be the result of sampling at a depth other than within the saline zone. This also could be due to the saline aquifer being at a shallower depth or it may not be present at those locations. The saline water at depth does not appear to have any influence on the shallower water wells at the time of sampling. If the piezometric surface of the saline water intersects with the water table aquifer, then there may be an influence of the water quality in the water table aquifer.

Of the numerous springs in the delineation zones, 16 of the springs have been sampled. Generally, levels of calcium, magnesium, sodium, potassium, and sulfate are all up to 60 times the SCL levels of 1.3 mg/l. There is considerable variation among the springs, due to the geology where the springs occur. One of the springs that was sampled was Big Spring. Levels of calcium and sulfate are higher than normal, but overall the water from Big Spring is excellent quality, supporting the local traditions for designating Big Spring as a ceremonial source of water.

Streams were sampled at 10 locations, including one USGS location that has been sampled since 1941, and some canals. Overall, these samples showed levels of calcium, magnesium, sodium, potassium, and sulfate that are higher than the specified SCLs. Two locations corresponded to Farm Creek and levels of all 5 constituents were significantly higher. Other samples were generally higher in only calcium, magnesium, and sulfate. However, samples from the lower reaches (southerly) are higher in these constituents than samples taken from the upper reaches in the north.

Generally the quality of the surface waters and springs are very good. Groundwater has considerable variation of water quality with depth. Additionally, there have been reports from private well owners that the groundwater tastes strange. Additional well sampling is needed to characterize the water table aquifer and determine if there are any water quality problems. Since there are 2 campgrounds upstream from the source springs, Whiterocks River should be sampled regularly for microbiological contamination. Additionally, the canals that pass over and adjacent to the source springs should be sampled regularly for all constituents including microbiological constituents, pesticides, and nutrients.

Source Water Delineation

Source water delineation zones include Zone A, the sensitive/critical area which extends 100 feet outward from the make-up well, the spring collection systems, and Big Spring to form a buffer zone. Zone B extends 15 miles upstream of the make-up well, the spring-collection system, and Big Spring within the limit of watershed boundaries. This includes Whiterocks and Uinta Rivers and associated tributaries. The buffer extends ½ mile on both sides of the rivers and tributaries. Zone C extends from 15 miles to 65 miles upstream or up to the edge of the Whiterocks and Uinta watersheds, including tributaries, with a buffer of 1000 feet on both sides of the rivers and tributaries.

The delineation method used for the water sources is a hybrid of the two methods defined by the State of Utah. Since all sources of the water supply represent groundwater sources, the initial Zone A is based on the delineation method used for groundwater sources as defined by the State of Utah. However, the springs may be impacted by surface water, so Zone B was based on the delineation method used for surface water as defined by the State of Utah. Zone C was based solely on the surface water method as defined by the State of Utah.

Zone A

According to the groundwater method outlined by the State of Utah, the critical zone should extend 100 feet from the source. This method was used for the spring collection system, the make-up well, and Big Spring. The total area of Zone A is 0.08 mi², or 50.7 acres. Zone A is shown for the make-up well, the spring collection systems, and for Big Spring in Figure 1.

Zone B

The spring collection systems are at depths of 9 to 20 feet below the surface in unconsolidated alluvial sediments. A report by EPIC Engineering and Loughlin Water Associates, LLC (2010) documents that seasonal fluctuations in nearby streams and canals are reflected in the volume of spring flow with a delay of 1 to 2 months. This indicates that this shallow groundwater source may be impacted by changes in the stage of streams and canals. A visual inspection of the spring collection areas confirmed that unlined canals are either adjacent to, or directly over the spring collection areas.

Based on this information, the surface water and groundwater methods outlined by the State of Utah were considered. First, the second zone for groundwater is specified to be based on a 250 day time of travel. The time of travel was calculated using the following relationship.

$$V_{sat} = K_{sat} \left(\frac{I}{n} \right).$$

Where V_{sat} is the saturated velocity of a fluid, K_{sat} is the saturated vertical hydraulic conductivity, I is the gradient, and n is the porosity of the sediments. Since I and n are dimensionless, V_{sat} inherits the units of K_{sat} . For K_{sat} , there were a range of values covering 4 orders of magnitude from 0.68 inches per day to 3401 inches per day. The highest and lowest were discarded, leaving values from 2 inches per day to 34 inches per day. The high value was used to compensate for variations of K_{sat} with depth. The gradient (I) was calculated for a range of 2.5% to 2.7%, relatively flat. And the porosity (n) for reworked glacial sediments combined with alluvium are generally in the range of 18% to 21%. High and low values of saturated velocity were calculated and the high value was used to compensate for sediment and depth variations. The results showed a 250 day time of travel equal to about 85 feet. This was compared with the information in the EPIC Engineering and Loughlin Water Associates, LLC (2010) report and found to match their calculations of 1 to 2 months for correlation between surface water and groundwater. Since 85 feet is still within the initial 100 feet of Zone A, this value was not used for Zone B. However, it should be noted that this is the approximate depth of the make-up well, indicating that anything that is absorbed at the surface near the well would only take 1 to 2 months to reach the intake area.

The surface water method outlined by the State of Utah indicates that the buffer zone should extend for ½ mile laterally from the river or stream, and extend 15 miles upstream or to the watershed boundary, whichever is encountered first. The canals and streams that influence the well and springs were determined and followed upstream for 15 miles. These streams were used to create the buffer zone for Zone B for the well and springs. This zone includes Whiterocks and Uinta Rivers, and the tributaries that flow into them. The total area for Zone B is 102.3 mi², or 65,639 acres.

Since Big Spring is located on the side of a canyon, the optional two mile radius delineation procedure outlined by the State of Utah was used for Zone B. This method uses a two mile radius, but is limited to 100 feet below the source and limited by streams or watershed boundaries. Since Big Spring is located in a small canyon above the Uinta River, this method was used to delineate an area bounded at the bottom by 100 feet, the watershed boundary at the top, and a combination of streams and ridges in all other areas. Zone B is shown for the well, springs, and Big Spring in Figure 1.

Zone C

According to the surface water method outlined by the State of Utah, Zone C extends from 15 to 65 miles upstream of the sources, or to the watershed boundary, whichever occurs first, with a buffer of 1000 feet on both sides of the streams. Streams that were used for Zone B were followed further upstream and selected. These streams were buffered to create Zone C and are shown in Figure 11. Since the area upgradient of Big Spring area is contained in Zones A and B as defined in those respective sections, it does not correspond to any areas upstream in Zone C and is not included in Zone C. The total area for Zone C is 130.8 mi², or 83,727 acres.

Inventory

Contamination can generally be thought of as coming from two different sources. The first is from a specific source called a point source, such as a leaking storage tank. The second, called a nonpoint source is where there is no specific source, such as runoff. The inventory revealed several point sources of potential contamination.

Methods

An inventory of the potential contaminant sources was completed for the delineated area. Potential sources of contamination were determined by onsite evaluations as well as researching databases. The databases reviewed include:

1. U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) – EnviroFacts database included EPA regulated facilities including hazardous waste generators, spill sites, surface discharge permits, impaired waters.
2. U.S. Bureau of Land Management – Well Database.
3. State of Utah – The state’s environmental databases, including landfills, treatment structures/discharge points, and hazardous waste sites were reviewed and included on the maps.
4. Utah Department of Natural Resources – Division of Oil, Gas, and Mining.
5. U.S. Department of Interior – Abandoned Mine Land Inventory System (AMLIS).
6. Major roads, railroads and petroleum transmission lines were identified in the delineation zone.
7. Local businesses were reviewed from the yellow pages directory to identify possible contaminant sources, such as dry cleaners, printers, chemical suppliers, etc.
8. Sites located within the delineation zone were reviewed to determine the likelihood and amount of potential contaminant onsite.

The potential contaminants can be divided into the following five categories:

Microbial – Microbial contaminants include viruses and bacteria from livestock operations, sewage treatment plants, septic systems and wildlife in concentrated areas. Examples include *E. coli* and *Cryptosporidium*.

Inorganics – Inorganic pollutants include metals and salts from sewage treatment plants, roads, farming, mining, and storm water runoff or oil and gas production. They also can occur naturally in the environment and be dissolved in runoff and carried to the lake. Examples include nitrogen, phosphorus, and heavy metals.

Organics – Organics include synthetic and volatile organic compounds and are by-products of industrial processes and petroleum production, and also can be found at gas stations, stormwater runoff and septic systems. Examples include benzene and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs).

Pesticides – Including insecticides and herbicides mainly come from agriculture runoff but also stormwater runoff.

Radioactive – Radioactive contaminants occur naturally and from the production of oil and gas and mining activities

Inventory Results

Tables 1 through 4 list the findings of the potential contaminant survey, shown graphically in Figures 17 through 26.

In the Zone B delineation section of this report the source waters (springs and make-up well) are most likely impacted by surface waters. Thus, the inventory for Zones B and C are based on surface water and limited to the extent of the delineated zones. Some sources of potential contamination include: oil wells; mines; public use areas; highway traffic; sewage disposal, agriculture, and storm runoff. There are also campgrounds and cemeteries.

Zone A Results

Zone A is based on the Whiterocks Spring, Uriah Heap Spring, the make-up well, and Big Spring, and is located in the Uinta River and Whiterocks River flood plains. The make-up well is located between the east and west channels of the Uinta River. The source of recharge to the make-up well is the east and west channels of the Uinta River. Table 1 lists the potential contaminant sources for Zone A. Figure 17 shows the 100-year flood zone passing directly over the Uriah Heap Spring collection systems and on both sides of the well. During flooding, the springs and well could be inundated by flood waters. Additionally, contaminants from upstream could be dislodged and carried downstream, and end up being deposited in Zone A where it could infiltrate into the recharge zone of the make-up well. Figure 18 shows streets and unlined canals. These unlined canals pass over and adjacent to both spring collection areas. Canal water and anything suspended or dissolved in the canal water can infiltrate directly into the soil above the spring collection pipes, resulting in a constant state of vulnerability. Several roads pass adjacent to both spring collection areas and storm runoff could wash spills on the roads into the soils as well as leach contaminants from trash and debris. The land use data shown in Figure 19 show that there are irrigated and non-irrigated lands and pastures. All lands are idle and not used for agriculture or grazing at this time. Figure 20 shows Big Spring. The only immediate threat to this spring is from trash from visitors, which can pose a contamination threat to the potable and aesthetic values of the spring water.

Table 1 - Zone A: Potential Contaminant Sources

Site	Site Description	GPS Coordinates
Flooding	100 Year Flood Zone	Non-Point Source
Septic Systems	Private Sewage Disposal	Non-Point Source
Runoff	Non-Point Source Contamination	Non-Point Source
Land use	Non-Point Source Contamination	Non-Point Source

Figure 17. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Supply Systems - 100-Year Flood Plain near Source-water Delineation Zones A and B.

Figure 18. Roads and Canals near Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Spring (EPIC Engineering and Loughlin Water Associated (2010).

Figure 19. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Supply Systems - Specific Land Use near Source-Water Delineation Zone A within Zone B.

Figure 20. Big Spring with Source-water Delineation Zones A and B.

Zone B Results

Zone B includes the upstream area from the springs to a point 15 miles upstream, with a ½ mile buffer on both sides of the rivers and tributaries. This includes the rivers and tributaries of Whiterocks River and Uinta River. All potential contaminant sources are shown in Figure 21 along with an explanation of each potential contaminant: Cultural features (campgrounds and cemeteries); Mine sites; National Pollution Discharge Elimination (NPDES) Facilities; Oil and Gas Wells; and Underground Storage Tanks. Further information on potential contaminants is listed in Table 2. Not all of the potential contaminant sites shown in Figure 21 were included for further analysis based on field work conducted in spring of 2014. During that visit, an examination of the potential contaminants sites was undertaken, and those to be considered for the analysis for susceptibility ratings, detailed in this report, Table 2, were confirmed. The most immediate threat to the springs in this zone are Harms Cemetery, just south of Whiterocks Springs. There is a high potential for contaminants being leached into the soils and into the groundwater that supplies Uriah Heap Springs to the south. There are several oil wells and mines in Zone B that are also potential threats. A sand and gravel mine (quarry pit) located on the south side of the hill where Whiterocks Springs are located appears to be abandoned and not considered to be a threat. However, there is a spring on the south side of this hill that flows through the quarry pit. There is an oil well located about halfway between Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs. Well records (U.S. Geological Survey) indicate that this well is active but shut in, and if there is any discharge from this well it could easily contaminate Uriah Heap Springs to the south. North, above Whiterocks Springs, there are several oil wells located in flood plain of the Whiterocks River channel and the hills above the river. According to the records all of these wells have been plugged and abandoned, but there is always a possibility of discharge from these wells. Near the north end of Zone B there is a campground and mine (quarry). A survey of this quarry indicates that it does not appear to be a potential source of contamination. However, the campground is located along the east bank of the Whiterocks River and has water spigots and toilets. The source of the water is a small spring collection system that is not treated. The toilets are of the vault type, comprised of lined cement vaults that are pumped periodically to remove the effluent. Figure 22 illustrates land use data for Zone B. Most of the land in this zone is idle and not irrigated. There are some parcels of land that are used for non-irrigated range pasture. Most of the irrigated land is used for alfalfa, hay and grasses, and pasture that could be a source of non-point contamination, especially when flooded or during a rain event. Land use is further subdivided in Figure 23, and graphed by percent of the total land use in Zone B.

Figure 21. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Supply Systems - Potential Contaminant Sources in Source-water Delineation Zone B.

Figure 21. Map Symbols – Explanation

Symbol

**And Map
Number**

	Type of Feature	NAME	FEATURE TYPE	COUNTY
1	Cultural	Elkhorn Guard Station	Locale	UINTAH
2	Cultural	Harms Cemetery	Cemetery	UINTAH
3	Cultural	Reeds Cemetery	Cemetery	UINTAH
4	Cultural	Uintah Canyon Youth Camp	Locale	DUCHESNE
5	Cultural	Farm Creek Grazing Enclosure	Locale	DUCHESNE
6	Cultural	White Rocks Cemetery	Cemetery	UINTAH
7	Cultural	Whiterocks Campground	Locale	UINTAH
8	Cultural	Uintah Meridian	Locale	UINTAH
9	Cultural	Whiterocks Fish Hatchery	Locale	UINTAH
10	Cultural	Uintah Powerplant	Locale	DUCHESNE

Symbol

**And Map
Number**

	Type of Feature	COUNTY	COMMODITY	SIZE
1	Mine	UINTAH	Sand and Gravel	S
2	Mine	UINTAH	Sand and Gravel	S
3	Mine	UINTAH	Sand and Gravel	S
4	Mine	UINTAH	SAO	L
5	Mine	UINTAH	Phosphate	M
6	Mine	UINTAH	Phosphate	S
7	Mine	UINTAH	Sand and Gravel	S

Symbol

**And Map
Number**

	Type of Feature	NPDES ID	ISSUING AGENCY	Primary Permit	FACILITY NAME
1	NPDES Facility	UTG589405	U.S. EPA	Sewerage Systems	WHITEROCKS
2	NPDES Facility	UTG130012	State	Fish Hatcheries And Preserves	UT DIV OF WILDLIFE- WHITEROCKS

Figure 21. Map Symbols – Explanation (Cont.)

Symbol ●	Type of Feature	Well ID	Liquid Production Type	Status	WELL NAME
And Map Number					
1	Oil and Gas Well	2196342	Oil	SHUT IN	MICHELLE UTE 7-1
2	Oil and Gas Well	110597495	Oil	INACTIVE	MICHELLE UTE 2-7A1E
3	Oil and Gas Well	125033017	Oil	INACTIVE	ASHLEY 7-2A1E
4	Oil and Gas Well	2188611	Oil	ACTIVE	UTE 1-8A1E
5	Oil and Gas Well	110603324	Oil	INACTIVE	WESTERN JD 1-6-A1E
6	Oil and Gas Well	110597452	Unknown	Plugged & Abandoned	WESTERN-JD 1-6-A1E
7	Oil and Gas Well	110603345	Oil	INACTIVE	WESTERN-JD 1-6A1E
8	Oil and Gas Well	110597492	Unknown	Plugged & Abandoned	VALENTINE FEE 1-33
9	Oil and Gas Well	2188595	Oil	SHUT IN	UINTAH-SAM 28-2R
10	Oil and Gas Well	2189106	Oil	ACTIVE	D MOON 1-23Z1
11	Oil and Gas Well	110604446	Oil	INACTIVE	NINA LOU 2-23Z1
12	Oil and Gas Well	110596936	Oil	Plugged & Abandoned	WHITE ROCKS U 2
13	Oil and Gas Well	110603182	Oil	Plugged & Abandoned	WHITE ROCKS U 1
14	Oil and Gas Well	110604186	Unknown	Plugged & Abandoned	CART HOLLOW 1
15	Oil and Gas Well	110596890	Unknown	Plugged & Abandoned	GILLBERGH 1
16	Oil and Gas Well	110600573	Unknown	Plugged & Abandoned	FULTON 2
17	Oil and Gas Well	110596922	Unknown	Plugged & Abandoned	WHITEROCKS 1
18	Oil and Gas Well	110597334	Unknown	Plugged & Abandoned	FEDERAL 24-1
19	Oil and Gas Well	110600565	Unknown	Plugged & Abandoned	MARIMON RANCH FEE 1
20	Oil and Gas Well	110597107	Unknown	Plugged & Abandoned	J F WALKER ET AL 1
21	Oil and Gas Well	110953239	Unknown	Plugged & Abandoned	SHELL 2 (CORE HOLE)
22	Oil and Gas Well	110953056	Unknown	Plugged & Abandoned	SHELL 2-A

Symbol ●	Type of Feature	FACILITY ID	Name	Local Streets	City	County
And Map Number						
1	Underground Storage Tank Facility	6831	GAS & MISC	INTERSECTION OF HIGHWAYS	WHITEROCKS	UINTAH
2	Underground Storage Tank Facility	6833	USDA FOREST SERVICE ELKHORN GUARD STATION	ROOSEVELT DISTRICT, ASHLEY NF	WHITEROCKS	UINTAH

Table 2 - Zone B: Potential Contaminant Sources

Site	Map Number	Site Description	GPS Coordinates
Oil Well	5	Western JD 1-6-A1E, Bluebell (PA)	40.42468° -109.93051°
Oil Well	6	Western-JD 1-6A1E, Bluebell (LA)	40.42635° -109.92707°
Oil Well	7	Western-JD 1-6-A1E, Bluebell (PA)	40.427° -109.92729°
Oil Well	9	Uintah-Sam 28-2R, Robidoux (S)	40.45313° -109.89055°
Oil Well	11	Nina Lou 2-23Z1 (LA), Bluebell	40.46566° -109.95936°
Oil Well	12	White Rocks U 2, Wildcat (PA)	40.51526° -109.92227°
Oil Well	13	White Rocks U 1, Wildcat (PA)	40.52679° -109.90333°
Oil Well	14	Cart Hollow 1, Wildcat (PA)	40.55316° -110.0256°
Oil Well	15	Gillbergh 1, Wildcat (PA)	40.55414° -109.96313°
Oil Well	16	Fulton 2, Wildcat (PA)	40.55771° -109.93942°
Oil Well	17	Whiterocks 1, Wildcat (PA)	40.56529° -109.92349°
Oil Well	18	Federal 24-1, Wildcat (PA)	40.55741° -109.93991°
Oil Well	19	Marimon Ranch Fee 1, Wildcat (PA)	40.56529° -109.92349°
Oil Well	20	J F Walker Et Al 1, Wildcat (PA)	40.56877° -109.9189°
Oil Well	21	Shell 2 (core hole), Wildcat (PA)	40.57259° -109.90923°
Oil Well	22	Shell 2-A, Wildcat (PA)	40.57261° -109.90926°
Mine	1	West Channel Uinta River Gravel Pit	40.434444° -109.933056°
Mine	2	Whiterocks Canal Sand and Gravel Pit	40.476667° -109.901389°
Mine	3	Farm Creek Sand and Gravel Pit	40.489722° -109.962778°
Mine	5	West Ashley Creek Phosphate Deposit	40.576111° -109.921389°
Mine	6	Phosphate Deposit Seg. 1	40.5775° -109.92°

Mine	7	Whiterocks Campground Gravel Pit	40.6225° -109.943056°
Elkhorn Guard Station	1	Locale	40.549127° -109.954052°
Harms Cemetery	2	Cemetery	40.468851° -109.904328°
Reeds Cemetery	3	Cemetery	40.524683° -109.957941°
Uintah Canyon Youth Camp	4	Locale	40.53607° -110.063777°
Farm Creek Grazing Enclosure	5	Locale	40.583849° -109.988498°
Whiterocks Cemetery	6	Cemetery	40.469406° -109.927106°
Whiterocks Campground	7	Sewage Disposal, Hazardous Waste	40.619682° -109.942386°
Whiterocks Fish Hatchery	9	Locale	40.483572° -109.955996°
Uintah Power Plant	10	Locale	40.537737° -110.066°
Gas Station	1	UST	40.468° -109.931°
USDA FS Elkhorn Guard Station	2	UST	40.549° -109.956°
Sewage Lagoons	Na	Public Sewage Systems	Non-Point Source
Pastures	Na	Irrigated Range Lands	Non-Point Source
Crops	Na	Irrigated Agricultural Lands	Non-Point Source
Septic Systems	Na	Private Sewage Disposal	Non-Point Source
Runoff	Na	Non- Point Source Contamination	Non-Point Source
Flooding	Na	100 Year Flood	Non-Point Source

Figure 22. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Supply Systems - Land Use within Source-water Delineation Zone B.

Figure 23. Sub-type of Land Use within Source-water Delineation Zone B.

Zone C Results

Zone C includes the area of upper Uinta and Whiterocks Rivers extending from the end of the Zone B to the edge of the watershed boundaries to the north and includes all tributaries. The zone has a 1000 foot buffer on both sides of the rivers and tributaries. Potential contaminant sources for this zone are shown in Figure 24 and listed in Table 3. Not all of the potential contaminant sites shown in Figure 24 were included for further analysis based on field work conducted in spring of 2014. During that visit, an examination of the potential contaminants sites was undertaken, and those to be considered for the analysis for susceptibility ratings, detailed in this report, Table 3, were confirmed. The primary sources of potential contaminants are the Paradise Campground and Paradise Guard Station, which are located along Paradise Creek, just below Paradise Park Dam. Although Paradise Campground does not have a water supply, most visitors bring their water with them or use water from the Paradise Creek. The toilets are comprised of lined cement vaults that are pumped periodically to remove the effluent. Additionally, the guard station probably has a similar type of toilet facility. The reservoir above the campground supplies constant flow into Paradise Creek. Several marshy areas, Dead Lake, and several smaller ponds indicate that the surface geology is saturated and the water table is at or near the surface throughout this small area. The soils in the canyon would not be able to absorb the effluent discharges, resulting in effluent saturated soils in this area that would drain into Paradise Creek, which feeds Whiterocks River. It is also worth noting that there are numerous small dams and impoundments in the upper Whiterocks and Uinta watersheds. Should any of these leak or fail, it would send a torrent of water downstream creating an instant flash flood and flushing any debris and contaminants downstream. There is a quarry in the Farm Creek sub-watershed that is classified as an active prospect. According to the record this is an iron ore prospect, and

depending on the activity and methods used it could be a source of contaminated mine water that drains into Farm Creek. Figure 25 illustrates land use data for this zone. Land classified in this category is comprised of riparian areas, lakes and ponds, reservoirs, streams, urban or no land use designation. No land in Zone C was listed for any type of agriculture, at the time of the study. Land use is further subdivided in Figure 26 and graphed by percent of the total land use in Zone C.

Figure 24. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Supply Systems - Potential Contaminant Source in Source-water Delineation Zone C.

Figure 24. Map Symbols – Explanation

Symbol

And Map Number	Type of Feature	NAME	FEATURE_TYPE	COUNTY
1	Cultural	Uinta Canyon Campground	Locale	DUCHESNE
2	Cultural	Paradise Guard Station	Locale	UINTAH
3	Cultural	Pole Creek Campground	Locale	DUCHESNE
4	Cultural	Shale Dugway	Trail	DUCHESNE
5	Cultural	Big Spring Recreation Area	Locale	DUCHESNE
6	Cultural	Uinta Canyon Summer Homes	Locale	DUCHESNE
7	Cultural	Zeagher Cabin	Locale	DUCHESNE
8	Cultural	Uinta Park Guard Station	Locale	DUCHESNE
9	Cultural	Uinta Picnic Area	Locale	DUCHESNE
10	Cultural	Whiterocks Lake Dam	Dam	UINTAH
11	Cultural	Crescent Lake Dam	Dam	DUCHESNE
12	Cultural	Moccasin Lake Dam	Dam	DUCHESNE
13	Cultural	Fox Lake Dam	Dam	DUCHESNE
14	Cultural	Wigwam Dam	Dam	DUCHESNE
15	Cultural	Papoose Lake Dam	Dam	DUCHESNE
16	Cultural	Uintah Meridian	Locale	UINTAH
17	Cultural	Zeagher Cabin	Locale	DUCHESNE
18	Cultural	Island Lake Dam	Dam	SUMMIT
19	Cultural	Paradise Park Dam	Dam	UINTAH
20	Cultural	Lower Chain Lake Dam	Dam	DUCHESNE
21	Cultural	Upper Chain Lake Dam	Dam	DUCHESNE
22	Cultural	Cliff Lake Dam	Dam	DUCHESNE
23	Cultural	Lake Atwood Dam	Dam	DUCHESNE
24	Cultural	Paradise Campground	Locale	UINTAH
25	Cultural	Uinta Canyon Forest Service Station	Locale	DUCHESNE
26	Cultural	Chepeta Dam	Dam	DUCHESNE

Symbol

And Map Number	Type of Feature	COUNTY	COMMODITY	SIZE
1	Mine	DUCHESNE	Iron (FE)	S

Figure 25. Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Supply Systems - Specific Land Use within Source-water Delineation Zone C.

Figure 26. Sub-type of Land Use within Source-water Delineation Zone C.

Table 3 - Zone C: Potential Contaminant Sources

Site	Map Number	Site Description	GPS Coordinates
Mine	1	Farm Creek Prospects (Iron)	40.611944° -110.0025°
Uinta Canyon Campground	1	Sewage Disposal	40.623289° -110.143779°
Paradise Guard Station	2	Sewage Disposal	40.66246° -109.912107 °
Pole Creek Campground	3	Sewage Disposal	40.678568° -110.059888°
Big Spring Recreation Area	5	Sewage Disposal	40.597734° -110.12989°
Uinta Canyon Summer Homes	6	Sewage Disposal	40.593568° -110.114889°
Zeagher Cabin	7	Sewage Disposal	40.623289° -110.089611°
Uinta Park Guard Station	8	Sewage Disposal	40.627456° -110.148501°
Uinta Picnic Area	9	Sewage Disposal	40.628844° -110.149612°
Zeagher Cabin	17	Sewage Disposal	40.608291° -110.087111°
Paradise Campground	24	Sewage Disposal	40.665793° -109.913496 °

Uinta Canyon Forest Service Station	25	Sewage Disposal	40.784675° -110.191°
Various Dams	10-15;18-23; 26	Flood Threat	Multiple
Shale Dugway Trail	Na	Trash, Sewage	40.752174° -110.19739°
Runoff	Na	Non- Point Source Contamination	

Inventory Update

The inventory and report should be updated regularly to remain current with land use and changes in the potential contamination sources. The time between revisions will depend on the amount of changes at the site. If there are few or no changes, the report could be updated with the revision of the sanitary survey. If there are significant changes, such as new potential contaminant sources near the intake, the report should be updated upon review of the site. This will allow any management decisions to be based on current activities and information.

Inventory Limitations

The inventory listed above was based on regulated and known facilities. It was also conducted using databases listed in the Methods section. Unregulated activities may have been overlooked due to lack of information.

Susceptibility

Susceptibility is a measure of how likely contaminants will reach the intake of the water system. How susceptible the system is depends on the barriers available to prevent the migration of contaminants, the past history of contaminant release both from accidental and unauthorized release, and the proximity of the intake to the source of contamination.

The susceptibility of the Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs is shown in Tables 4 through 6. Each table is followed by a narrative of the contaminant rating score for each potential contaminant source. The EPA further describes the contaminant rating. A high contaminant rating would be a serious or a potentially serious threat to human health such as petroleum related contaminants, microbiological contaminants, nitrate/nitrites, and chemicals with a Maximum Contaminant Level (MCL) goal of zero (potential carcinogens) present in medium to large quantities. A moderate rating would be the same as described in the high rating but present in small quantities or large quantities of chemicals with an MCL above zero or treatment techniques available on site. A low rating would be the same as medium but present in small quantities.

For the remaining columns: location within the critical zone implies that it is within the delineated area; natural barriers are features that slow down or block contaminant movement, possibly reducing the contaminant concentration or neutralizing it naturally; intake integrity is used to add a point to intakes over 10 years old, implying the older intakes would be more susceptible to contamination; and the history of contamination column is if there has been a contaminant detected in the water source.

The susceptibility of the system can be used to determine the proper management of the source water protection area. The table is from the *Water Education Foundation; Protecting Drinking Water: A Workbook for Tribes* (Water Education Foundation, 2000), and provides a way of prioritizing protection activities of the potential contaminants. With possible scores ranging from 1 – 8, the assignment of High, Medium and Low could be broken out with High = 5-8, Medium = 3-4, and Low = 1-2

Table 4 - Zone A: Susceptibility Ratings

Item	Potential Contaminant Source	Contaminant Rating High = 3 Moderate = 2 Low = 1	Location within critical zone yes = 1 no = 0	Natural Barriers good = 0 moderate = 1 absent = 2	Intake Integrity 0 = < 10 yrs. 1 = > 10 yrs.	History contaminant detected 1 = yes 0 = no	Total
1.	Flooding	2	1	2	1	0	6
2.	Septic Systems	1	1	1	1	1	5
3.	Runoff	1	1	1	1	0	4
4.	Land Use	1	1	1	1	0	4

Table 4 Narrative

A. Contaminant Rating

1. Flooding – A moderate rating was given since this well is located in the flood plain and within the zone defined as the 100 year flood zone.
2. Septic Systems – A low rating was given due to the small number of systems in this zone.
3. Runoff – The runoff was given a low rating because the roads in the delineated area are used infrequently, the limited agricultural activity, and relatively flat slope.
4. Land Use – The land use was given a low rating because all of the land within the zone is not being used for agriculture or grazing.

B. Location

All sites are located within the delineated area for Zone A.

C. Natural Barriers

Flooding was given a moderate rating because of the proximity of surface water sources to the springs. All other contamination sources were given a low rating since all of these sources are either not active or isolated by elevation and/or flow directions away or around the springs.

D. Intake Integrity

The water system and sources are more than 10 years old.

E. History of Contamination

There were two incidents where coliform was detected in the water in July and August, 2013. Surface waters have been sampled primarily for dissolved metals.

F. Total

The total score is an indicator of the susceptibility of the source waters to various contaminant sources listed within delineation Zone A. With possible scores ranging from

1 – 8, the assignment of High, Medium and Low is indicated as follows: High = 5-8, Medium = 3-4, and Low = 1-2.

Table 5 - Zone B: Susceptibility Ratings

Item	Potential Contaminant Source	Contaminant Rating High = 3 Moderate = 2 Low = 1	Location within critical zone yes = 1 no = 0	Natural Barriers good = 0 moderate = 1 absent = 2	Intake Integrity 0= < 10 yrs. 1= > 10 yrs.	History contaminate detected 1 = yes 0 = no	Total
1.	Oil Wells	2	1	1	1	0	5
2.	Mines/Quarries	2	1	1	1	0	5
3.	Cemeteries	2	1	1	1	0	5
4.	Campground	2	1	1	1	0	5
5.	Guard Stations	1	1	1	1	0	4
6.	Youth Camp	1	1	1	1	0	4
7.	Grazing Enclosure	1	1	1	1	0	4
8.	Fish Hatchery	2	1	1	1	0	5
9.	Power Plant	1	1	1	1	0	4
10.	Gas Station	3	1	1	1	0	6
11.	Sewage Lagoons	2	1	1	1	0	5
12.	Irrigated Pastures	2	1	1	1	0	5
13.	Irrigated Crops	2	1	1	1	0	5
14.	Septic Systems	1	1	1	1	0	4
15.	Runoff	1	1	1	1	0	4
16.	Flooding	1	1	2	1	0	5

Table 5 Narrative

A. Contaminant Rating

1. Oil Wells – A moderate rating was given as a precaution since the age and construction details of the wells are not known. All of these wells are either LA or Plugged and Abandoned (PA), except one well which is S. The rating can be adjusted higher or lower if additional construction information about these wells is obtained.
2. Mines/Quarries – A moderate rating was given since most of the mines are open pit quarries, some with springs or small streams flowing through them. Enhanced runoff caused by flooding and/or snow melt could flush sediments or mining byproducts into Whiterocks River, increasing turbidity or loading the river with byproducts.
3. Cemeteries – A moderate rating was given because of the potential for leaching of chemicals used in this type of work and especially for the proximal location of one cemetery just upstream of Uriah Heap Springs.
4. Campground – A moderate rating was given since the campground is located adjacent to Whiterocks River, in the flood plain, and has a potential to contaminate the river with effluent and spills of hazardous materials.
5. Guard Stations – A low rating was given because of the low risk of effluent leakages and the considerable distance upstream of the locations.

6. Youth Camp – Although there is a significant risk associated with this location, it is located in the Uinta River basin which isolates it from most of the water source. Therefore, a low rating was given to this location.
7. Grazing Enclosure - Although there is a significant risk associated with this location, it is located in the Uinta River basin which isolates it from most of the water source. Therefore, a low rating was given to this location.
8. Fish Hatchery - Although there is a significant risk associated with this location, it is located in the Uinta River basin which isolates it from most of the water source, but could be a serious contaminant source in the Uinta River. Therefore, a moderate rating was given to this location.
9. Power Plant – The main threat from this location is from dam failure or releases due to flooding. Therefore, a low rating was given to this location.
10. Gas Station – This location is associated with an UST and is located near the community of Whiterocks making it a significant threat. Therefore, a high rating was given to this location. Upon confirmation of removal and remediation of this location, the rating can be lowered.
11. Sewage Lagoons – These locations are a potentially serious threat. Therefore, a moderate rating was given to this location.
12. Irrigated Pastures – These areas could be a source of infiltrated contamination that could also be washed off the surface with runoff. Therefore, a moderate rating was given to this location.
13. Irrigated Crops – These areas could be a source of infiltrated fertilizer based contamination that could also be washed off the surface with runoff. Therefore, a moderate rating was given to this location.
14. Septic Systems – A low rating was given due to the small number of systems in this zone.
15. The runoff was given a low rating because the roads in the delineated area are used infrequently, and the limited agricultural activity.
16. Flooding - A moderate rating was given since the 100 year flood zone for Whiterocks River impacts the lower reaches of the river and has the potential to flush contaminants downstream.

B. Location

All of the sites are located within the delineated area for Zone B.

C. Natural Barriers

All sources were given a moderate rating since all potential contaminants are not in direct contact with Whiterocks River. The only exception is for flooding, which could have a direct impact on the flows downstream.

D. Intake Integrity

The spring collection systems are more than 10 years old.

E. History of Contamination

There have been no contaminants detected in the source water.

F. Total

The total score is an indicator of the susceptibility of the Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs System to various contaminant sources listed within delineation Zone B. With possible scores ranging from 1 – 8, the assignment of High, Medium and Low is indicated as follows: High = 5-8, Medium = 3-4, and Low = 1-2.

Table 6 - Zone C: Susceptibility Ratings

Item	Potential Contaminant Source	Contaminant Rating High = 3 Moderate = 2 Low = 1	Location within critical zone yes = 1 no = 0	Natural Barriers good = 0 moderate = 1 absent = 2	Intake Integrity 0= < 10 yrs. 1= > 10 yrs.	History contaminate detected 1 = yes 0 = no	Total
1.	Mines/Quarries	1	1	0	1	0	3
2.	Campgrounds	2	1	1	1	0	5
3.	Guard Stations	1	1	0	1	0	3
4.	Recreation Areas	2	1	1	1	0	5
5.	Summer Homes	2	1	1	1	0	5
6.	Cabins	2	1	1	1	0	5
7.	Picnic Areas	2	1	1	1	0	5
8.	Forest Service Station	1	1	0	1	0	3
9.	Trail	1	1	0	1	0	3
10.	Dams	1	1	1	1	0	4
11.	Runoff	1	1	1	1	0	4

Table 6 Narrative

A. Contaminant Rating

1. Mines and Quarries – These locations were given a low rating because of the distance from the source waters.
2. Campgrounds – A moderate rating was given since the campgrounds are located adjacent to Paradise Creek and Pole Creek, and have the potential to contaminate the streams with trash, effluent, and spills of hazardous materials.
3. Guard Stations – A low rating was given since the guard stations are located near streams, and have a minimal potential to contaminate creeks.
4. Recreation Areas – A moderate rating was given to these locations because of the potential for contamination from trash and effluent.
5. Summer Homes – These locations are on septic systems which could contaminate the streams over time. Therefore, a moderate rating was given to these locations.
6. Cabins – These locations are on septic systems which could contaminate the streams over time. Therefore, a moderate rating was given to these locations.
7. Picnic Areas – These locations could contaminate the streams with trash and contamination dumped in the soils and streams over time. Therefore, a moderate rating was given to these locations.
8. Forest Service Station – This location was given a low rating because of the low impact on this facility on the environment.
9. Trail – This location was given a low rating since most of the trail is far enough away from streams to buffer it from any contamination.
10. Dams – These locations were given a low rating since the only threat is dam failure.
11. Runoff – The runoff was given a low rating because the roads in the delineated area are used infrequently, but overland runoff can flush sediments and contaminants into the streams.

B. Location

All sites are located within the delineated area for Zone C.

C. Natural Barriers

Most of the contaminant sources have good natural barriers. However, those that are proximal to streams were given moderate ratings.

D. Intake Integrity

The spring collection systems are more than 10 years old.

E. History of Contamination

There have been no contaminants detected in the source water.

F. Total

The total score is an indicator of the susceptibility of the Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs System to various contaminant sources listed within delineation Zone C. With possible scores ranging from 1 – 8, the assignment of High, Medium and Low is indicated as follows: High = 5-8, Medium = 3-4, and Low = 1-2.

Source Water Management

Management of existing potential contaminant sources is the final portion of a source water protection plan and can involve public education and best management practices. Examples include methods of reducing runoff through the use of buffer zones, public education for the proper use of fertilizers and pesticides, and proper containment of animal waste at concentrated feed operations. Another type of management can involve zoning ordinances to limit possible contaminant sources from being developed in the delineation zone or applying additional requirements for existing sites to prevent contamination. An example of this would be restricting future energy development from the delineated zone.

Management of contaminants entering the delineation zones by people or vehicles, can be managed through the implementation of an emergency response plan. An emergency response is a tool to control contamination threats within the delineated zones to reduce these threats to the water supply.

Citations

ASTM International E1689-95 (2008) Standard Guide for Developing Conceptual Site Models for Contaminated Sites, West Conshohocken, PA: ASTM International

EPIC Engineering, and Loughlin Water Associates, LLC, 2010, Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs Evaluation, April 2010, Prepared for the Ute Indian Tribe, 29 p.

Hansen, Wallace R., 1986, Neogene Tectonics and Geomorphology of the Eastern Uinta Mountains in Utah, Colorado and Wyoming, U.S. Geological Survey Professional Paper 1356, 78 p.

Hintze, L.F., Willis, G.C., Laes, D.Y., Sprinkel, D.A., and Brown, K.D., 2000, Digital Geologic Map of Utah: Utah Geological Survey, in cooperation with U.S. Geological Survey, 1:500,000.

Lambert, P.M., Marston, T., Kimball, B.A., and Stolp, B.J., 2011, Assessment of groundwater/surface-water interaction and simulation of potential streamflow depletion induced by groundwater withdrawal, Uinta River near Roosevelt, Utah: U.S. Geological Survey Scientific Investigations Report 2011-5044, 47 p.

Sprinkel, Douglas A., 2007, Interim geologic map of the Vernal 30' x 60' quadrangle, Uinta and Duchesne Counties, Utah, and Moffat and Rio Blanco Counties, Colorado: Utah Geological Survey, Open File Report, OFR-506 CD.

Sprinkel, Douglas, A., 2014, The Uinta Mountains, A Tale of Two Geographies and More: Utah Geological Survey Notes, Volume 46, No. 3, September 2014.

State of Utah, 2001, Source Protection: Drinking Water Source Protection for Surface Water Sources. R309-605, Date of Enactment or Last Substantive Amendment: August 27, 2001
Notice of Continuation: March 13, 2015, Authorizing, and Implemented or Interpreted Law: 19-4-104(1)(a)(iv).

State of Utah, 2012, Source Protection: Drinking Water Source Protection for Ground-Water Sources. R309-600, Date of Enactment or Last Substantive Amendment: November 15, 2012
Notice of Continuation: March 13, 2015, Authorizing, and Implemented or Interpreted Law: 19-4-104(1)(a)(iv).

U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 2016, Conceptual Site Model—Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Springs in the Whiterocks and Uriah Heap Public Water Supply Systems, E. Ervin-Blankenheim, February 2016.

U.S. Geologic Survey, National Water Information (NWIS) Database. USGS

Water Education Foundation, 2000, Protecting Drinking Water: A Workbook for Tribes: Water Education Foundation, July 11, 2000, 109 p.

Appendix A. Stratigraphy (Sprinkel, 2007)

Stratigraphic Column for the South Flank of the Uinta Mountains

